

Complex Iodates of Tin and Antimony.

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No iodates of tin and antimony have yet been described. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to prepare the iodates of these metals and study their properties.

By the action of a nitric acid solution of iodic acid on penta-hydrated stannic chloride stanni-iodic acid (I) or di-hydroxy-tetra-iodato stannic acid (II) was obtained according to the proportions of iodic acid used. When stanni-chlorides of the alkali metals were substituted for the hydrated stannic chloride, compounds of the type (IV, salts corresponding to I) were invariably obtained. With sodium iodate stannic chloride gave tetra-hydroxy-di-iodato stannic acid (III); while potassium iodate and potassium stannichloride gave a double compound (V) of hexa-iodato potassium stannate with mono-hydroxy-penta-iodato potassium stannate.

I

II

III

IV

(M = Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs or NH₄)

V

By the calcination of (I) a substance was obtained corresponding to the empirical formula Sn₁₄O₂₁I. This

substance is characterised by its extreme stability and its insolubility in any solvent.

Iodic acid and chloro-antimonic acid give a compound of the composition $[(HO)_3Sb(IO_3)_3]H$, tri-hydroxy tri-iodato antimonic acid.

Considering the analogy between H_2SnCl_6 and H_2PtCl_6 and between their products of hydrolysis, and recalling the resemblance of stannic acid and stannates with $H_2Pt(OH)_6$ and its salts, the constitution of these iodates may be represented according to the above scheme (*cf.* Werner and Pfeiffer, *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 17, 182; Pfeiffer, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2466; Belluci and Parravano, *Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1904, (v), 13 (ii), 307, 324; *ibid.*, 1905, (v), 14 (v), 457; *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, 45, 142).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Di-hydroxy-tetra-iodato Stannic Acid (II).

The compound was obtained in a granular form by adding to a slight excess of iodic acid dissolved in dilute nitric acid (concentrated acid of sp. gr. 1.4 diluted with an equal volume of water) a calculated amount of a solution of pentahydrated stannic chloride crystals in water acidified with a drop of strong hydrochloric acid and evaporating the clear liquid on the water-bath. The mixture was then cooled and the substance was washed three times by decantation with dilute nitric acid (10 c.c. concentrated acid per 100 c.c. water), filtered and washed several times on the funnel with the same liquid. The substance was then dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid.

Found (sample dried overnight) : Sn = 13.54; HIO_3 = 79.00.

Found (Sample dried for several days): Sn = 14.12; HIO_3 = 81.45. $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{H}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{IO}_3)_4]$ requires Sn = 13.92; HIO_3 = 81.87 per cent.

Stanni-iodic Acid (I).

To a large excess of iodic acid dissolved in dilute nitric acid (20 c.c. concentrated acid per 100 c.c.), the calculated amount of stannic chloride solution (*cf.* previous preparation) was added drop by drop with constant stirring; the mixed solution was then evaporated on the water-bath when a crystalline white powder was obtained. The mixture was then cooled and the crystals washed and filtered as in the previous case. They were then dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid. (Found: Sn = 10.24, 10.25; IO_3 = 88.84, 89.04. $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{HIO}_3$ requires Sn = 10.16 and IO_3 = 89.6 per cent.)

Potassium Stanni-iodate.

Potassium stannichloride dissolved in the least quantity of water was added to a solution of iodic acid in dilute nitric acid (10 c.c. concentrated acid per 100 c. c.), with constant stirring. A granular precipitate was readily obtained which was washed with dilute nitric acid of the same strength and dried in vacuo over sulphuric acid. (Found: Sn = 9.58, 9.38, 9.61; IO_3 ' = 83.73, 83.8; K = 6.16, 6.32. $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{KIO}_3$ requires Sn = 9.54; IO_3 ' = 84.2 and K = 6.62 per cent.)

Ammonium Stanni-iodate.

The curdy white precipitate obtained by mixing the calculated amount of ammonium stannichloride with an excess of iodic acid was dissolved by adding concentrated nitric acid. Concentrated ammonia was then added to partially neutralise the excess of free nitric acid. A

granular precipitate formed and readily settled. It was then washed and dried as in the previous case. (Found: Sn=9.93, 10.0; IO_3' =86.8, 86.98; NH_4 =3.05. $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{IO}_3$ requires Sn=9.87; IO_3' =87.14 and NH_4 =2.99 per cent.)

Rubidium Stanni-iodate.

Rubidium stannichloride dissolved in a fairly dilute nitric acid was added to a solution of an excess of iodic acid in the same solvent. The stanni-iodate separated in a fine granular form on standing for some time. The substance was then washed and dried as in the case of the potassium compound. (Found: Rb=12.85; Sn=8.76; IO_3' =77.7. $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{RbIO}_3$ requires Rb=12.76; Sn=8.88 and IO_3' =78.33 per cent.)

Cæsium Stanni-iodate.

Cæsium stannichloride dissolved in moderately strong nitric acid was slowly added to an excess of dilute nitric acid solution of iodic acid. The mixed solution was evaporated on the water-bath when granular white precipitate gradually separated out. The precipitate was washed and dried as in the previous case. (Found: Cs=18.11; Sn=8.33; IO_3' =72.85. $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{Cs}(\text{IO}_3)$ requires Cs=18.53; Sn=8.35 and IO_3'' =73.17 per cent.)

Sodium Stanni-iodate.

A solution of sodium stannichloride, acidified with a drop of dilute nitric acid, was gradually added to a solution of an excess of iodic acid in moderately strong nitric acid (concentrated acid diluted with an equal volume of water) with constant stirring. The solution on concentration on the water-bath gave a granular precipitate which was filtered on the pump, washed several times with dilute nitric acid (6 c.c. of concentrated acid, sp. gr. 1.4 per 100 c.c.) and dried as usual. (Found:

Na=3.95; Sn=10.04; $\text{IO}_3=86.18$. $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{NaIO}_3$ requires Na=3.78; Sn=9.8 and $\text{IO}_3'=86.1$ per cent.)

Lithium Stanni-iodate.

About 8 gms. of iodic acid were dissolved in fairly strong nitric acid (35 c.c. of concentrated acid per 100 c.c.). Two gms. of stannic chloride and 6 gms. of lithium chloride dissolved in about 10 c.c. of water were added drop by drop to the solution of iodic acid. The mixed solution, on evaporation on the water-bath, gave a crystalline precipitate. It was filtered, washed and dried as in the case of the sodium compound. (Found: Li = 1.13; Sn = 10.12; $\text{IO}_3'=87.88$; $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{LiIO}_3$ requires Li=1.18; Sn=10.06; $\text{IO}_3'=88.76$ per cent.)

Double Compound of Hexa-iodato Potassium Stannate and Mono-hydroxy-penta-iodato Potassium Stannate (V).

When potassium iodate was substituted for iodic acid in the preparation of potassium stanni-iodate, a compound was obtained which on analysis gave the following results and differed from potassium stanni-iodate in composition. (Found: K = 6.75, 6.8; Sn = 10.28, 10.24; $\text{IO}_3'=81.58$, 81.45. $\text{K}_2\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_6 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_5(\text{OH})$ requires K = 6.68; Sn = 10.19 and $\text{IO}_3'=82.44$ per cent.)

Tetrahydroxy-di-iodato Stannic Acid (III).

To an excess of sodium iodate dissolved in dilute nitric acid (10 c.c. of strong acid per 100 c.c.) was added a solution of the calculated amount of stannic chloride in the least amount of water. A thick white precipitate was obtained which was allowed to settle, filtered, washed with dilute nitric acid and dried as usual. (Found: Sn=22.11, 21.9; $\text{IO}_3'=66.5$, 66.6; I = 46.96. $\text{Sn}(\text{IO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Sn=22.07; $\text{IO}_3'=65.33$ and I=47.17 per cent.)

Properties of Stanni-iodic Acids and their Salts.

With the exception of hexa-iodato acid and its lithium salt, the compounds are all amorphous white powders. They all react acid to litmus. Like most of the iodates they are insoluble in water but are gradually hydrolysed by it being completely broken by boiling water into stannic oxide and iodic acid or alkali iodates. They are easily reduced by reducing vapours and organic matters, with liberation of iodine. The freshly prepared lithium and sodium stanni-iodates are soluble in dilute and strong nitric acids but on drying they completely lose this property.

Action of Heat on Hexa-iodato Stannic Acid.

When the hexa-iodato stannic acid was ignited in a porcelain crucible, copious vapours of iodine were given off and a light yellow residue was left even after strong ignition over the full flame of a Teclu burner. There was no loss of tin during the ignition as the *total* amount of it remained unchanged in the ignited product. The residue was unaffected by water, alcohol, sulphur dioxide, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and carbon bisulphide. Different samples of the ignited residue on analysis gave a fairly constant composition. (Found : Sn = 77.57, 77.89 ; I = 5.95, 5.99. $\text{Sn}_{14}\text{O}_{21}\text{I}$ requires Sn = 78.25 and I = 5.96 per cent.)

Trihydroxy-tri-iodato Antimonic Acid.

A solution of antimony pentachloride in strong hydrochloric acid was slowly added to an excess of a concentrated aqueous solution of iodic acid. A precipitate appeared after stirring for a few seconds. It was filtered on the pump and washed with a small amount of water. It was then dissolved in excess of water acidulated with

a few drops of dilute iodic acid and evaporated on the water-bath when a white powder separated from the solution. It was filtered, and washed as before and dried over sulphuric acid in vacuum. (Found: Sb=17·13, 17·1; IO_3' =74·41, 73·86; I=53·71. $\text{Sb}(\text{IO}_3)_3(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Sb=17·21; IO_3' =75·31 and I=54·66 per cent.)

The substance is an amorphous white powder and reacts acid towards litmus. It is soluble in water and the solution remains clear even after addition of ammonia; while cold dilute caustic soda solution slowly precipitates the oxide of antimony, concentrated nitric acid also precipitates hydrated antimonous oxide from the solution.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS.

Stanni-iodates.

The substance was treated with hydrochloric acid mixed with a little sulphurous acid to reduce the iodate. The solution was then carefully neutralized with ammonia and then the tin was precipitated as SnO_2 by boiling with ammonium nitrate. The alkali metals were estimated as sulphate by evaporating the filtrate with a little sulphuric acid. Iodic acid was estimated by treating the substance with a solution of potassium iodide in hydrochloric acid and titrating the liberated iodine with sodium thiosulphate. Iodine was also estimated as silver iodide in the filtrate from tin oxide by first decomposing the substance with sulphurous acid alone.

The substance $\text{Sn}_{14}\text{O}_{21}\text{I}$ was analysed by fusing with sodium carbonate and sulphur. Tin was precipitated as sulphide from the solution of the fused mass in water by the addition of acetic acid. Iodine was estimated as silver iodide from the filtrate after removing the sulphuretted hydrogen by evaporation and finally by oxidation with a little ammonical hydrogen peroxide.

Antimony Compounds.

The substance was dissolved as in the case of tin iodate by a mixture of hydrochloric and sulphurous acid. The solution was treated with an excess of yellow ammonium sulphide and the antimony was precipitated as sulphide by adding acetic acid. By decomposing the substance with sulphurous acid alone iodine was also estimated as silver iodide from the filtrate from antimony sulphide. Iodic acid as such was determined by treating the substance with an acid solution of potassium iodide as in the case of tin compounds but in this case as both antimonious (Sb^{III}) antimony and iodic acid contributed to the liberation of iodine so the amount corresponding to the reduction of antimony from the pentavalent to the trivalent condition was deducted from the total amount of iodine liberated.

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